

doi:10.5281/zenodo.15429392

The Moderating Impact Of Age At Marriage And Communication As Predictors Of Full-Shell Marriage Among Married Teachers In Delta State

¹Ogbodu Rita Oghenerumue; ²Prof. Okorodudu R. I & ³Prof. (Mrs.) A. Onayase

¹Department of Educational Psychology/Guidance and Counselling
College of Education, Mosogar, Delta State, Nigeria
Email: ogbodurita@gmail.com/ Phone: 07031514277

^{2,3}Department of Guidance and Counselling
Delta State University Abraka, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

The study adopted a correlational research design. The target population comprised all registered married teachers in public secondary schools across Delta State. According to data obtained from the Post-Primary Education Board (PPEB), the population entail 8,526 married teachers (2,720 males and 5,806 females). A sample size of 370 married teachers was drawn using a multi-stage sampling technique. In the first stage, two public secondary schools were randomly selected from each of the 25 Local Government Areas (LGAs) across the three Senatorial Districts of Delta State. From the selected schools, a total of 118 male teachers and 252 female teachers were included in the study. Data for the study were collected using a structured questionnaire titled Communication Factors Questionnaire (CFQ), Full-Shell Marriage Scale adapted Marital Happiness Index (MHI) by Terman (1938). To ensure the reliability of the instruments, Cronbach's Alpha was computed and Full-Shell Marriage Scale was 0.82 and Communication Factors Questionnaire yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.54. The data collected were analysed using descriptive statistics such as mean, median, and standard deviation, as well as inferential statistics. Pearson correlation and regression analyses were conducted at a 0.05 level of significance. From the analysis of data, it was found that there is a significant relationship between communication and full-shell marriage, while age at marriage did not significant moderate the impact of communication on full-shell marriage. Based on the findings, it was recommended that School and marriage counsellors should encourage married teachers to prioritize communication skills and conflict resolution abilities through couples therapy, communication workshops, or self-help resources to enhance marital satisfaction. Also, School and marriage counsellors should offer married teachers practical strategies and support to navigate challenges, such as stress management techniques and communication skills training. And finally, School and marriage counsellors should provide married teachers with treatment or techniques on how to address challenges effectively, irrespective of demographic characteristics.

Keywords: Full-Shell Marriage, Communication, Age at Marriage, Full –Shell Marriage, Teachers

INTRODUCTION

Marriage is anticipated to be a harmonious partnership, characterized by mutual love and care, bringing a sense of fulfillment to both individuals involved. Human beings find their fulfilment being a couple. It fills the physical and psychological void which exists in humans, if they are alone. Developing effective

communication skills requires dedication and effort. As rising divorce rates indicate, many couples struggle to achieve a level of mutual understanding, leaving conflicts unresolved and tensions to escalate. When misunderstandings deepen and respect diminishes, couples may eventually separate due to an inability to resolve their issues.

Marriage is termed Full-shell when it is abounding with nice and wonderful experiences characterized with love, kindness, forgiveness and mutual satisfaction. It is that type of marriage that does not consider divorce as a solution to the issues faced but the couples try to work out their differences and live happily. Makinde (2004) defined marriage as a union between a man and a woman, emphasizing the physical connection enabled by their sexual complementarity. The purpose of the marriage union is to foster happiness, security, cultural enrichment, and the development of a sense of responsibility, thereby ensuring its perpetuation. Commitments are made between the man and the woman who agreed to be in a marriage relationship. This is done by exchange of vows privately or publicly with family members, friends and well-wishers present. The exchange of vows implies that the man and woman who are referred to as couple after being pronounced man and wife are expected to stick together through all circumstances.

Full-shell Marriages may be found among couples that understand what marriage is all about such as having an understanding that everything must not be rosy every time, there are likely to be disagreement occasionally between each other but such couples are ready to stay together and enjoy their marriage no matter the circumstances surrounding the marriage. Full-shell marriages according to Levinger (as cited in Nimitz, 2011) is a typology of marriage that experience high level of marital stability and satisfaction, it can also be referred to as that marriage in which the partner experiences marital stability, adjustment and satisfaction and for the purpose of this study we are going to take features of marital stability, happiness and satisfaction as full-shell marriages.

According to Aroson and Alikit (1997), as cited in Ojukwo (2016), marital stability traditionally refers to the equilibrium between personal interests and shared values, which fosters steady and consistent behaviors both within individuals and between spouses. Marital stability refers to the probability that a marriage will remain intact without ending in dissolution or divorce.

According to Okorodudu (2010), full-shell marriages are characterized by feelings of love, trust, respect, and faithfulness between partners. These marriages involve making one's spouse a best friend, genuinely liking them as a person, and viewing marriage as a long-term commitment. A healthy and stable marriage, where both partners are satisfied, contributes to the strength of society, as the family serves as its foundation. A full-shell marriage is characterized by stability, happiness, and satisfaction, which are key indicators of a strong and enduring marital relationship. Such marriages are often found among couples who have a deep understanding of the realities of marriage, recognizing that not every moment will be perfect. These couples acknowledge that occasional disagreements are inevitable but remain committed to sustaining their relationship despite challenges. A full-shell marriage is fundamentally a stable marital relationship, where stability refers to the likelihood of the marriage remaining intact without leading to separation or divorce. Married couples in full-shell marriages rarely consider divorce and experience deep fulfillment in their relationship. Marital stability is a crucial aspect of marriage, as it significantly impacts individual well-being, family dynamics, and society as a whole.

Factors which may contribute to building and sustaining a full-shell marriage include communication. Communication, as a factor, can also predict the success of a full-shell marriage. It plays a crucial role in stabilizing and strengthening a marriage. Effective communication requires practice and significant effort, as it is essential for resolving conflicts and fostering the growth of a partnership. According to Hybels and Weaver (2001), communication involves the sharing of information, ideas, and emotions, encompassing not only spoken and written words but also body language, personal mannerisms, and style. Communication is a fundamental aspect of human interactions, serving as the pillar that upholds peaceful coexistence and mutual understanding. In the context of marriage, communication is especially vital (Esere, 2002). It is the key to a strong and healthy relationship, enabling partners to express love and care. Good communication involves honing the skills of listening, as well as expressing thoughts and feelings.

The importance of communication in marriage cannot be overstated. As Esere (2002) notes, strong and healthy relationships rely on open and effective communication, which enables partners to express love, care, and understanding. To maintain a successful marriage, couples must develop skills in both expressing their thoughts and actively listening to one another. Many individuals enter marriage with the hope of a lifetime of happiness, yet sustaining a loving and fulfilling relationship requires continuous effort from both spouses. Angel (2008) describes marriage as a complex journey that can either bring immense joy or become a burden, depending on the level of effort invested. Several key factors contribute to marital success, including trust, love, time, friendship, honesty, sincerity, and, most importantly, effective communication. A lack of communication can significantly weaken a marriage, making it susceptible to breakdown. Esere (2002) emphasizes that communication serves as the lifeline of any meaningful relationship, while Olagunju and Eweniyi (2002) describe it as a remedy for struggling marriages.

With divorce rates on the rise (Adegoke & Esere, 1998), improving communication between spouses has become more critical than ever. Many marital issues worsen in the absence of communication, whereas effective dialogue helps resolve conflicts and strengthen relationships. Jolin, K. (2007) asserts that communication is the cornerstone of a successful marriage, and without it, relationships are unlikely to endure in today's world, where divorce is increasingly common.

Idowu and Esere (2007) further highlight that poor communication is a leading cause of failed relationships, with more than half of breakups attributed to inadequate dialogue between partners. A long-lasting relationship requires strong communication skills, including the ability to express emotions and thoughts while also attentively listening to one's partner. The skill of listening is arguably even more vital than speaking, as couples grow closer when they take the time to truly understand each other's perspectives. This does not mean one should refrain from expressing opinions, but rather that both partners should acknowledge and consider each other's viewpoints. Additionally, communication is not solely verbal; many individuals express themselves through actions. Recognizing these nonverbal cues can enhance understanding and connection within a marriage. However, failure to observe and respond to these signals can lead to misunderstandings and discord.

Over the past decade, various researchers have explored factors that contribute to either strengthening or weakening marital relationships. For instance, Yusuf (2015) examined key indicators of marital instability, while Adeyemi (1991) investigated the causes of divorce and separation. Additionally, Isiaka (2005) conducted an empirical study on the relationship between divorce and spousal communication, concluding that ineffective communication often precedes marital dissolution. Noller and Fitzpatrick (2010) found a significant correlation between communication patterns and marital stability. Poor communication, on the other hand, has been linked to a higher likelihood of divorce, marital separation, and behavioral issues in children.

Yelsma and Athapilly (2018) conducted a cross-cultural study examining the relationship between communication practices and marital satisfaction among Indian and American couples. Their research compared marital satisfaction scores across three types of marriages: Indian arranged marriages, Indian love marriages, and American companionate marriages. Findings indicated that individuals in arranged marriages reported higher levels of marital satisfaction compared to those in love or companionate marriages. Additionally, the study revealed that verbal communication was more strongly correlated with dyadic satisfaction in Indian love marriages and American companionate marriages than in Indian arranged marriages. With the established connection between marital cognition, communication, and relationship satisfaction, Gordon et al. (2009) examined these relationships further. Using three self-report assessments—the Dyadic Adjustment Scale, the Inventory of Specific Relationship Standards, and the Communication Patterns Questionnaire—they collected data from 387 couples within a community sample. The results suggested that communication plays a greater role in marital stability for women with strong relationship-focused values, whereas this effect was not observed among men.

Age is a crucial factor in determining the likelihood of a stable and fulfilling marriage. Maturity, often associated with age, plays a significant role in how couples handle marital challenges. The importance of

age in marriage stems from the assumption that maturity increases with age, equipping individuals with better problem-solving skills, emotional intelligence, and patience. Marrying at a younger age can present challenges, as individuals may not yet possess the self-awareness, life experience, or stability necessary for long-term commitment. A study by Hashmi, Khurshid and Hassan, (2017) suggested that age differences between spouses can influence marital satisfaction and stability. The research indicates that men report higher levels of marital satisfaction when married to younger spouses, particularly in the early years of marriage. Moreover, the age at which individuals enter marriage influences their level of emotional and psychological preparedness, which affects their ability to adjust to marital responsibilities and maintain a stable union. Research has shown that marriages entered into during teenage years tend to be more fragile. This has been attributed to what Oppenheimer (2008) describe this construct as the “maturity effect.” Younger individuals are more likely to have unrealistic expectations of marriage and may lack a full understanding of both their own long-term aspirations and those of their partners. According to Oppenheimer, early marriages often involve partners choosing each other based on characteristics that are still evolving, which increases the likelihood of incompatibility over time.

Contrary to the expectation that marrying at an older age always enhances marital stability, some studies suggest mixed outcomes. For instance, Ebebuwa-Okoh (2011) found that age at marriage does not necessarily moderate the relationship between key marital factors such as emotional expression, financial management, communication, and work involvement. Similarly, Mohammadi, et. al, (2016) observed that younger couples may be more likely to let go of minor disputes rather than holding grudges that create long-term tension. Research by Jose and Alfons (2017) examined multiple variables influencing marital satisfaction, including age, number of children, employment status, and length of marriage. Their findings indicated that individuals who married later were more likely to stay married. However, they also noted that younger couples who divorced were more likely to remarry. Interestingly, their study also suggested that older individuals at the time of first marriage experienced greater difficulty adjusting to marital life. In particular, middle-aged adults displayed more adjustment challenges than both younger and elderly individuals in the study. Overall, while maturity and life experience generally contribute to marital success, age alone might not guarantee a fulfilling relationship. The relationship between age and marital stability remains complex, with research presenting diverse perspectives on how age at marriage influences long term relationships.

Statement of the Problem

The home is the foundational unit of society, and marriage serves as the primary means of societal growth through childbearing. Marital instability, has far-reaching consequences, affecting not only the family unit but also society as a whole. When marriages become unstable, challenges arise in the upbringing of children, potentially leading to increased rates of juvenile delinquency and a decline in societal harmony.

It has been observed by the researcher that some married teachers in Delta State are not carrying out their duties in the classroom like having up to date lesson note, they give their notes to student to copy for them and even during the teaching learning process they are carried away with thought from home, marital instability as a result of stress that involves lack of communication, which hinders job performance and satisfaction. Studies and reports has shown in Nigeria that the increasing rate at which some marriages are crisis riddled, separation and divorce threatened is unimaginable and have assumed a worrisome dimension that in the near future, the purpose of marriage might be effected. Reports of marital breakdowns, divorces, and their effects on families, especially children, are frequently featured in both electronic and print media. Furthermore, the Chief Justice of Delta State that between January and May 2020, 157 petitions were filed by people seeking dissolution of marriage and noted that the trend of marital dissolution is scary , ugly and worrisome (independent Newspaper, 2020). This implies that the marriages of most married teachers which include teachers in Delta state are conflict riddled. Marital instability has direct negative effects on the well-being of spouses, children, families, and society as a whole.

The researcher has observed that many married teachers in Delta State are not experiencing full-shell marriages. This is evidence in lack of trust between couples, often stemming from poor communication as

well as criticism, when partners do not effectively communicate their needs, concerns, and aspirations, misunderstandings and suspicions arise, eroding the foundation of trust. When a marriage is plagued by the above issues, the foundational element of love within the marriage crumbles.

As a result, married teachers facing such difficulties may find it challenging to focus on their work. The stress and emotional turmoil from an unstable marriage can spill over into their professional lives, reducing their effectiveness and ability to achieve educational goals. Teachers, who are crucial in shaping the minds of future generations, may struggle with job performance, leading to a broader negative impact on the educational system. As such, the need to curtail and stem the tide of marital separation and divorce made the researcher to investigate the relationship between poor communication and full-shell marriage.

The researcher is concerned about how certain factors may influence full-shell marriages among married teachers. Could psychological, environmental and situational factors predict full-shell marriage among married teachers in Delta State? As a result, the paper investigated communication as a determining predictors of full-shell marriage.

Research Questions

1. What is the relationship between Communication (COM) and Full-Shell Marriage (FSM) among married teachers in Delta State
2. What is the moderating impact of Age At Marriage (AAM), in the relationship between Communication (COM) factor and Full-Shell Marriage (FSM) among married teachers in Delta State?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant relationship between communication and full-shell marriage among married teachers in Delta State. Communication factor with full-shell marriage among married teachers in Delta State
2. There is no significant moderating impact of Age At Marriage (AAM) in the relationship between Communication (COM) and full-shell marriage (FSM) among married teachers in Delta State

Purpose of the study

The purpose of the study is to investigate the relationship between communication and Full-shell marriage among married teachers in Delta State. Specifically, the study sought to:

- * Ascertain the level of relationship between communication and full-shell marriage among married teachers in Delta State;
- * Examine the moderating impact of age at marriage, in the relationship between communication with full-shell marriage among married teachers in Delta State;

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a correlational research design. The target population comprised all registered married teachers in public secondary schools across Delta State. According to data obtained from the Post-Primary Education Board (PPEB), the population entail 8,526 married teachers (2,720 males and 5,806 females). A sample size of 370 married teachers was drawn using a multi-stage sampling technique. In the first stage, two public secondary schools were randomly selected from each of the 25 Local Government Areas (LGAs) across the three Senatorial Districts of Delta State. From the selected schools, a total of 118 male teachers and 252 female teachers were included in the study. Data for the study were collected using a structured questionnaire. The Communication Factors Questionnaire (CFQ) was self-developed by the researcher and comprised three subscales designed to measure compatibility, sexual differences, and communication practices among married teachers. The Full-Shell Marriage Scale was adapted from established instruments, including the Marital Happiness Index (MHI) by Terman (1938) and the Dyadic Adjustment Scale (DAS) by Spanier (1976). To ensure the reliability of the instruments, Cronbach's Alpha was computed using SPSS. The reliability coefficient for the Full-Shell Marriage Scale was 0.82, indicating high internal consistency. The Communication Factors Questionnaire yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.54, which, though moderate, was deemed acceptable for exploratory studies. The administration of the questionnaire was conducted directly by the researcher with the assistance of trained

research aides. The data collected were analysed using descriptive statistics such as mean, median, and standard deviation, as well as inferential statistics. Pearson correlation and regression analyses were conducted to examine the relationships among the variables at a 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: *What is the relationship between Communication (COM) and Full-Shell Marriage (FSM) among married teachers in Delta State?*

Table 1: Correlation Matrix and Descriptive Statistics of Communication with Full-Shell Marriage (FSM)

Variable	Mean	SD	COM	FSM
COM	16.02	3.01	1	
FSM	66.67	11.74	.46**	1

Determining Factor/Independent: Communication.

Dependent: Full Shell Marriage

Table 1 reveals the inter-correlation matrix and descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation of Communication (COM) with Full-Shell Marriage (FSM). The correlation values for Communication = 0.46. It showed that Communication (COM) positively correlated to each other with Full-Shell Marriage (FSM).

Research Question 2: *What is the moderating impact of Age at Marriage (AAM) on the relationship between Communication (COM), with Full-Shell Marriage (FSM) among married teachers in Delta State?*

Table 2: Correlation Matrix and Descriptive Statistics of Mean And Standard Deviation Moderating Impact of Age At Marriage (AAM) on the Relationship Between Communication (COM), and Full-Shell Marriage (FSM).

Variable	Mean	SD	COM	AAM	FSM
COM	16.02	3.01	1		
AAM	1.66	.70	.00	1	
FSM	66.67	11.74	.46**	-.06	1

Predictor (s): Communication and Age at Marriage.

Dependent: Full Shell Marriage

Table 2 revealed the inter-correlation matrix and descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation of the moderating impact of Age At Marriage (AAM), on the relationship between Communication (COM), and Full-Shell Marriage (FSM). It reveals that Age At Marriage (-.06), negatively moderated the relationship between Communication (COM) with Full-Shell Marriage (SM).

Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between Communication (COM) with Full-Shell Marriage (FSM)

Table 4.3: Linear Regression Analysis of Communication (COM) with Full-Shell Marriage (FSM)

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
Regression	15700.69	4	3925.17	4.59	0.00	
Residual	35589.41	368	96.71			
Total	51290.09	372				

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	Remark
	B	Std. Error	Beta (β)			
(Constant)	29.43	4.41	6.67		.00	
Communication	.92	.21	.24	4.30	.00	Significant

a. Predictor(s): Communication

b. Dependent Variable: Full Shell Marriage

Table 4.3 shows the multiple regression analysis of the relationship between Communication (COM.) with Full-Shell Marriage (FSM). It revealed that $F = 40.59$; $p = .00 \leq 0.05$. Testing the hypothesis at a 0.05 level of significance, the p-value is less than the alpha value of 0.05, which reveals a significant relationship. Therefore, the null hypothesis, which stated that there is no significant relationship between Communication (COM.) with Full-Shell Marriage (FSM), was rejected. This showed that there was a significant relationship between there was a significant relationship between Communication (COM.) with Full-Shell Marriage (FSM).

The beta weight was computed to determine the contribution of each of the predictor variables to Full-Shell Marriage (FSM). The beta weight for Communication = .24, $t = 4.30$, $p = .00$. This indicated that the communication correlated with Full-Shell Marriage (FSM).

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant moderating impact of Age At Marriage (AAM), in the relationship between Communication (COM) with full-Shell marriage (FSM)

Table 4: Multiple Regression Analysis of Moderating Impact of Age at Marriage (AAM), in the Relationship between Communication (COM) and Full-Shell Marriage (FSM)

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Remark
	B	Std. Error	Beta (β)			
(Constant)	29.43	4.41	6.67		.00	
Communication	.92	.22	.24	4.28	.00	S
Age at Marriage	-.62	.73	-.04	-.85	.39	NS

a. Predictor(s): Communication and Age at Marriage.

b. Dependent Variable: Full Shell Marriage

Table 4 reveals the multiple correlation and regression analyses on the moderating impact of Age At Marriage (AAM) in the relationship between Communication (COM) and full-shell marriage (FSM). The beta (β) values for Communication = .24, $t = 4.28$, $p = .00$ as moderated by Age at Marriage (AAM) = -.04, $t =$

.85, $p=.39$. Testing the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance for moderating impact, the beta (β) weight was used to determine if there is moderating impact of age at marriage, in the relationship between communication and full-shell marriage, the p-values are higher than the alpha value, which showed a no significant moderating impact. Therefore, the null hypothesis, which stated that there is no significant moderating impact of Age At Marriage (AAM), in the relationship between Communication (COM) and Full-Shell Marriage (FSM), was retained. This is because the (β) of each moderator variable was not statistically significant at the 0.05 level.

DISCUSSION

The finding demonstrated a significant relationship between communication and Full-Shell Marriage. Communication encompasses a wide range of contextual elements and circumstances that shape daily marital experiences and interactions. Communication pertains to the effectiveness and quality of both verbal and non-verbal interactions. Communication is a crucial component of a healthy and thriving marriage. Partners who communicate openly, respectfully, and with empathy are better equipped to handle conflicts, express their needs, and support one another. By fostering trust and understanding, communication strengthens marital interactions and enhances overall relationship satisfaction. Couples who demonstrate adaptability, emotional support, and resilience in the face of challenges are more likely to maintain a strong, fulfilling marital bond. Those who navigate stress together and sustain open lines of communication are better positioned to preserve the stability and satisfaction of their relationship.

Good communication reinforces the marital bond and deepens the couple's connection. As the findings of this study support the research of Gottman and Gottman (2007), which underscored the importance of effective communication skills in sustaining marital satisfaction. According to their study, open and transparent communication enables couples to manage conflicts constructively, build trust, and navigate challenges, all of which are critical components of Full-Shell Marriage. Furthermore, Christensen and Gottman (2010) suggested that couples who openly express both positive and negative emotions tend to form stronger relationships. Their research highlighted that supportive and validating communication fosters emotional security and connection, both of which are essential for a fulfilling marital experience.

The second finding also revealed that age at marriage did not significantly moderate the relationship between communication and Full-Shell Marriage. This indicated that this demographic characteristic did not meaningfully alter the relationship between communication and key components of Full-Shell Marriage. Age at marriage, often viewed as an important life milestone, did not emerge as a significant moderator in the association of communication within marriage. This suggests that whether couples married at a younger or older age, communication as a factor maintained a consistent influence on marital satisfaction. Couples across various stages of their marital journey exhibited similar associations between communication and their overall marital satisfaction.

CONCLUSION

The findings of this study highlight the significant influence of communication on the foundation of a Full-Shell Marriage. This factor contribute to a couple's compatibility and their ability to build a strong emotional connection. Open, honest communication fosters emotional intimacy and trust. When couples clearly communicate and define their expectations and actively work toward fulfilling them, they are better equipped to navigate challenges and maintain a resilient, satisfying marriage. However, demographic variables such as age at marriage do not significantly moderate the relationship between these factors and marital satisfaction. This suggests that couples from diverse age range at marriage can still achieve a fulfilling marriage, even if they navigate different influences like communication pattern in different ways. Ultimately, the study underscores the complexity of marital satisfaction, emphasizing that communication shape a Full-Shell Marriage, in the way couples manage expectations and engage with significant factors that determines the overall quality and fulfilment of their marital union.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were advanced:

1. School and marriage counsellors should encourage married teachers to prioritize communication skills and conflict resolution abilities through couples therapy, communication workshops, or self-help resources to enhance marital satisfaction.
2. School and marriage counsellors should offer married teachers practical strategies and support to navigate challenges, such as stress management techniques and communication skills training.
3. School and marriage counsellors should provide married teachers with treatment or techniques on how to address challenges effectively, irrespective of demographic characteristics.

REFERENCES

- Adegoke, A.A. & Sire, M.O. (1998) Sources of stress and coping strategies among divorces in Ilorin Metropolis, The counsellors Journal of the counselling association of Nigeria 16(1), 127 -233
- Adeyemi, E. (1991) causes of divorces and separation as perceived by married couples in Tertiary institution Ilorin metropolis, Unpublished M.Ed. project, University of Ilorin
- Angel U, (2008) Mastering Interpersonal communication skills between you and your spouse New York : Sage publications Inc.
- Aronson, R. A., Wilson, E. N., & Alkert, O. E. (2007). Effects of communication and conflict management skills in enhancing the interpersonal relationships of Seventh-day Adventist couples in Lagos, Nigeria. *Journal of Communication and Culture*, 4(3), 11-21.
- Christensen, C. T., & Gottman (2010). Forgiveness intervention. *Journal of Consulting and Clinical Psychology*, 65(6), 1042-1046.
- Ebenuwa-Okoh, E. E. (2011). Sex and age as moderators of the relationship between environmental variables and marital adjustment among married persons. *Educational Research*, 2(1), 745-751.
- Esere, M. O. (2002). *Communication in marriage relationship*. In L.A. Yahaya, M.O. Esere, J. O. Ogunsanmi, & A. O. Oniye (2008). *Marriage, sex and family counselling*. Ilorin: Unilorin
- Gottman, J. M. (2009). *What predicts divorce? The relationship between marital processes and marital outcomes*. Lawrence Erlbaum.
- Gordon, A., Impelt, E.A., Kogan, A. & Oveis C. (2009): To Have and To Hold : Gratitude promotes Relationship Maintenance in intimate Bonds , *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*
- Hashmi, J., Khurshid, R. D & Hassan, F (2017). Forgiveness as a psychotherapeutic goal with elderly females. *Psychotherapy: Theory, Research, Practice, Training*, 30(4), 658-667.
- Hybels, S. A. & Weaver, A. C. (2001). *Communicating effectively*. Glencoe McGraw-Hill.
- Idowu, A.I. & Esere, M.O. (2007), *Communication in counselling , A Multidimensional Perspective , Ilorin . Tim Sal Publishers*
- Isiaka, A.A. (2005) *The Relationship between spousal communication and divorce*. Unplubished Masters Project University of Ilorin Nigeria
- Independent Newspaper, , May 2020
- Jolin, K. (2007) *Ways to encourage communication between your spouse and you*: San Diego: Academic press.
- Jose, O., & Alfons, V. (2006). The effect of forgiveness on marital satisfaction in relation to marital stability. *Contemporary Family Therapy*, 28, 251-261. *Journal of Business Communication*, 25, 53-64.
- Levinger, G. (1965). Marital cohesiveness and dissolution; An integrative review. *Journal of Marriage and the Family*, 27, 19-28
- Makinde, B.O. (2004) *Human sexuality education and marital guidance*. Raytel communications. *Journal of Marriage and the Family*, 52, 832-843.

- Mohammadi, M., Arjomandnia, A. A., & Razini, H. H. (2016). The relationship between couples' attachment style and self-efficacy with happiness and marital satisfaction. *International Academic Journal of Humanities*, 3(7), 8-17.
- Nimtz, M.A. (2011). *Satisfaction and contributing factors in satisfying long-term marriage: A phenomenological study*. Liberty University ProQuest Dissertation Published
- Noller P. Fitzpatrick, M.A.(2010) , Communication concerns ad Satisfaction in early marriage , in Vangelisti, A.L. Reli H.T. , stability and change in relationship , (pp 129-155) Cambridge University Press , <https://doi.org/10.1017/CB0978511499876.009>
- Okorodudu R.I. (2010). *Fundamental of marriage and family counselling*. University Printing Press.
- Ojukwu, J. E. (2014). Social construction of manhood in Nigeria: Implications for male responsibility in reproductive health. *African Population Studies*, 19(2), 1-20.
- Olagunju, O. P. & Eweniyi, G. B. (2002). Communication: A strategy in conflict resolution among organisational workers. *The Counsellor*, 19(1), 66-78
- Oppenhemier (2008) A Theory of marriage Timming ,Assortive Mating under varying Degree of uncertainty , *America Journal Sociology* 94 (4),563 -591
- Yelsma, P., & Athapilly, K. (2008). Marital satisfaction and communication practice: comparison along Indian and American couples. *Journal of Comparative Family Studies*, 19(1), 37-54.
- Yusuf, S. T. (2005). *Indices of marital stability as perceived by University of Ilorin lecturers*. Unpublished B.Ed. project, University of Ilorin, Nigeria.
- Zainah, A. Z, Nasir, R., Ruzy, Suliza, H., & Noraini, M. Y. (2012). Effects of demographic variables on marital satisfaction. *Asian Social Science*, 8(9), 46-49.